

N-(N⁴-Aryl-N¹ piperazinylmethyl)-4-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-piperidine-2,6-diones : CNS Depressants

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Five N-(N⁴-aryl-N¹-piperazinylmethyl)-4-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-Piperidine-2,6-diones(III) were synthesized by the reaction of 4-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-piperidine-2,6-dione(I) on N-aryl piperazines(II) in presence of HCHO. The piperidine dione(I) required for the synthesis, was prepared by an alternate route. Mass spectrum of III was studied.

SINCE Saches¹ first reported the synthesis of N-piperidinomethyl phthalimide by the reaction of phthalimide with piperidine in presence of formaldehyde, the amidomethylation reaction has been applied to various amides² and imides using secondary bases.

Significant CNS depressant activity associated with 4-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-piperidine-2, 6-dione (I)³ and N¹-(substituted piperidine-2,6-dione-1-yl methyl)-N⁴-aryl piperazines⁴⁻⁸ prompted us to synthesize N-(N⁴-aryl-N¹-piperazinylmethyl)-4-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-piperidine-2, 6-diones (III) as possible tranquilizers.

Scheme : 1

N-aryl piperazines were prepared by C. B. Pollard's method⁹. 4-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-piperidine-2, 6-dione (I)³ was synthesized by different route using corresponding glutacnic acid as starting compound. 3-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-glutaconic acid¹⁰ (IV) was reduced by Na-Hg in alkaline medium to furnish corresponding glutaric acid (V). The acid (V) on refluxing with Ac₂O gave the anhydride¹¹ (VI), which when fused with urea yielded I in good yield (Scheme 2).

Scheme : 2

TABLE—I N-(N⁴ARYL-N¹-PIPERAZINYLMETHYL)-4-(4'-METHOXYPHENYL)-PIPERIDINE-2,6-DIONE(III)

No.	R	Molecular formula	Yield %	M.P. °C*	N%** Found	N%** Calcd.
a.	H	C ₂₃ H ₂₇ N ₃ O ₃	80	164-5	10.60	10.69
b.	3-CH ₃	C ₂₄ H ₂₉ N ₃ O ₃	75	128-9	10.24	10.32
c.	4-CH ₃	C ₂₄ H ₂₉ N ₃ O ₃	52	183-4	10.30	10.32
d.	3-Cl	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ N ₃ O ₃ Cl	48	96-7	9.72	9.83
e.	4-Cl	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ N ₃ O ₃ Cl	63	145-6	9.69	9.83

*All melting points are uncorrected.

**C and H analysis was found satisfactory.

Compounds IIIa to IIIe (Table.1) were synthesized by the condensation of 4-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-piperidine-2, 6-dione (I) with N-arylpiperazines (II) in presence of aq-HCHO in ethanol. *o*-Tolyl and *o*-chlorophenyl piperazines, failed to react with I. Formation of III was ascertained by their elemental analysis and spectral studies. The NMR spectrum of IIIa (R=H) showed a sharp singlet of bridge

methylene protons (joining piperazine and piperidinedione moieties) at 4.98 δ (2H). The downfield shift is presumably due to the electron attracting dicarboximido group attached to the methylene group. IR of IIIa showed peaks at 1680 cm^{-1} 1730 cm^{-1} characteristic of imidic keto groups.

Mass spectrum of IIIa.

The reversibility of amidomethylation reaction is well documented¹². Compound III when boiled in alcohol for a longer time gave back I. This led us to study the mass spectral fragmentation of a representative compound IIIa, which would throw light on the stability of the methylene bridge.

Compound IIIa, showed a low intensity molecular ion peak at m/e 392, indicating the instability of the molecular ion. The initial ionization could take place on either imidic N-atom or on piperazine tert.-N-atoms. The base peak at m/e 161 represents the most abundant ion (VIII) formed by scission *a*, while the second prominent ion at m/e 175 (IX) is formed by the scission *b*.

Counterpart of ions VIII and IX are ions at m/e 232 and m/e 218: Both of them are of low intensity, probably they readily fragment further to ions like X and XI, similar to the reported succinimide fragments¹³. On the other hand phenyl piperazine part may undergo fragmentations to ions like XII to XVI as reported in the case of N,N-diphenyl piperazine¹⁴. Interestingly the loss of CO or CO₂ was not observed.

The fragmentation outlined above clearly indicates the site of instability, that is, the methylene bridge.

Experimental

(I) 4-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-piperidine-2,6-dione : 2.2 gm. 3-(4'-methoxyphenylglutaric) anhydride (VI) was mixed with 4 gm. of urea. The mixture was heated to its melting point and held at this temp. for 1 hour. It was cooled and the solid was crystallized from water to give 1.9 gm. of I, m. p. 174-5° (87%).

(IIIa) N-(N⁴-phenyl-N¹-piperazinyl methyl)-4-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-piperidine : 2,6-dione : 2.2 gm. (0.01m) I, 1.61 gm. (0.01 m) phenyl piperazine and 1 ml formalinh (40% aq.) were added to 25 ml. ab. alcohol. The mixture refluxed for 45 min. After cooling the crystals of the product separated out, filtered and washed with alcohol to give 3.20 gm. IIIa (80%). m.p. 177-8° (dec.). Analysis : Found : C, 70.2 ; H, 6.92 ; N, 10.69 percent. Calcd. : C, 70.0 ; H, 7.10 ; N, 10.62 percent.

Pharmacological screening of these compounds is in progress.

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References

1. F. SACHS, *Ber. deut. Chem. Ges.*, 1898, 31, 1232.
2. A. EINHORN, *Ann. Chem. Liebigs.* 1905, 343, 207 ; 1908, 316, 113.
3. F. A. EL-TELBANY, K. M. GHONEIM, K. M. KHALIFA, *Pharmazie*, 1977, 32, 22.
4. C. WADE, B. R. VOGT. *U.S.* 3,947, 452 March 30, 1976 (C. A. 1976, 85, 32880⁴)
5. WU YAO-HUS, K. R. SMITH, J. W. RAYBURN, J. W. KISSEL, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1969, 12, 876.
6. WU YAO-HUS, J. W. RAYBURN, L. E. ALLEN, H. C. FERGUSON, J. W. KISSEL, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1972, 15, 477.
7. WU YAO-HUS, *U.S.* 3,398, 151, Aug. 20, 1968 (C. A. 1969, 70, 4143⁵).
8. O. L. MNDZHOYAN, L. M. PETROSYAN, N. E. AKOPYAN, *Arm. Khim. Zh.*, 1971, 24, 492. (C. A. 75, 129485²).
9. C. B. POLLARD, L. G. MARCDOWELL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 2199.
10. V. M. BHAVE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 137.
11. D. B. LIMAYE and G. R. GOGATE, *J. Univ. Bomb.*, 1935, 2, 140.
12. H. HELLMANN in 'Newer Methods of Preparative Organic Chemistry' (Ed.) W. Foerst, Academic Press, New York, 1963, Vol.II, p. 277.
13. A. M. DUFFIELD. H. BUDZIKIEWICZ and C. DJERASSI, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 87, 2913.
14. Y. FUKIKO, F. YASUYOSHI and N. TOMIHIRO, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1972, 45, 280.